

ONE DIMENSIONAL MODEL USING ALGORITHM FOR BLOOD VESSEL

Dilafroz Nurjabova

Phd student of Tashkent University of Information Technologies,

100084, Tashkent ,Uzbekistan

dilyaranur1986@gmail.com

Abstract. Particular emphasis has been put on the effects of the connective tissues surrounding the arterial wall. The equations governing the motion of the system are sought in the Laplace transform space and their relevant solutions are obtained in the transformed domain. Laplace inversion is also carried out, by employing numerical techniques.

Key words: blood vessel, one dimensional model, flow dynamics

Introduction. In the field of biofluid dynamics, mathematical and computational models have been widely used to understand the flow of blood in both healthy and diseased arteries. These models typically involve the consideration of vessel geometry, material properties, governing equations, and appropriate initial and boundary conditions. One-dimensional (1D) fluid-structure interaction models have emerged as a useful tool for studying the dynamics of blood flow in the human arterial network.[3] These models can capture important aspects of the problem, such as the effects of the surrounding connective tissues on the arterial wall, in a computationally efficient manner.

Methods. The one-dimensional model algorithm for blood flow in arteries is based on the assumption that the vessel can be represented as an isotropic elastic tube filled with a viscous incompressible fluid representing blood.[4] The governing equations for the system are derived using principles of fluid mechanics and solid mechanics, and typically involve the continuity equation, momentum equation, and a

constitutive law for the arterial wall. Here, this approach is used to develop a model in which vessels remodel structurally in response to local stimuli derived from shear stress, circumferential wall stress, and oxygen partial pressure. The “rules” applied are based as far as possible on known and accepted aspects of vascular responses to hemodynamic and metabolic stimuli, additional assumptions invoked are chosen so that they have at least a plausible biological mechanism. The resulting model can be used to predict vascular responses to changes in hemodynamic or metabolic conditions, such as hypertension or altered oxygen consumption as well as functional consequences of changes in the intrinsic vascular adaptation characteristics.

Results. The resulting system of equations can be solved using numerical techniques, such as the finite element method, to obtain the pressure, flow rate, and other relevant variables along the length of the artery. In here introduces the application of the finite element method to biofluid dynamics problems. Only a short description of blood flow problems is provided. The one-dimensional fluid-structure interaction approach to the human arterial network and three-dimensional patient-specific flow approach to blood flow in arteries are presented. The topics covered include image segmentation and diseases. Some examples are also presented to demonstrate the presented approaches. Mathematical and computational models for blood flow in normal and diseased arteries include vessel geometry, material properties, governing equations, and proper initial and boundary conditions. Models for stenosis, carotid, coronary, aorta, abdominal aortic aneurysm, pulmonary capillaries, graft, and stent are presented, with controlling factors and research focuses for each model discussed and proper references cited. Recent trends and potential applications for artery modeling are also discussed.

Methodology. The flow mechanism is subjected to a pulsatile pressure gradient due to the normal functioning of the heart, as well as a single cycle of body acceleration. The one-dimensional model algorithm has been shown to be an effective approach for simulating blood flow in arteries, and can provide insights into the effects of various factors, such as the surrounding connective tissues, on the dynamics of the system. The artery is modelled as an isotropic elastic tube filled with a viscous incompressible fluid representing blood. The flow mechanism of the present study is subjected to a pulsatile pressure gradient owing to the normal functioning of the heart, together with a single cycle of body acceleration. Particular emphasis has been put on the effects of the connective tissues surrounding the arterial wall. The equations governing the motion of the system are sought in the Laplace transform space and their relevant solutions are obtained in the transformed domain. Laplace inversion is also carried out, by employing numerical techniques.

Discussion. The one-dimensional fluid-structure interaction model for blood flow in arteries has several advantages over more complex three-dimensional models. It is computationally efficient and can be applied to the entire arterial network, allowing for the study of the global behavior of the cardiovascular system.

Conclusion. The one-dimensional model algorithm is a useful tool for analyzing and simulating the dynamics of blood flow in arteries, and can provide valuable insights into the effects of various factors on the system. The results, which demonstrate the uniqueness of solutions of the Navier-Stokes equations for a viscous incompressible fluid under given initial conditions, as well as with the condition of continuity, are based on theoretical studies of mathematical hydrodynamics. There is a theorem on the existence and uniqueness of solutions for the Navier-Stokes equations, which states that under given initial conditions and the condition of continuity, the Navier-Stokes equations have a unique solution with respect to the components of the fluid

velocity. This means that any problem in hydrodynamics that is modeled by the Navier-Stokes equations has a unique solution [5,7].

Fig.1. Estimate the range of velocity minimum and maximum

This theorem has important implications for many fields of science and technology, such as aerodynamics, geophysics, biomechanics and medicine. For example, in medicine, it can be used to simulate blood flow in the heart and blood vessels.

Magnitude	Minimum	Maximum
U:=x	-1.99845	1.9992
V:=y	-1.99727	1.99955
W:=z	-0.995313	0.995265
P:	-3.95736	-0.0081647

Estimate the velocity

Table1.1.
range of

REFERENCES

[1]. Landau L.D., Lifshits E.M. Teoreticheskaya fizika. Gidrodinamika. – M.: Nauka, 1950. –T. 4 – 735 p.
 [2].Ladyzhenskaya O.A. Matematicheskie voprosy dinamiki vyazkoi zhidkosti neszhimaemoizhidkosti // – M.: Nauka, 1970. – 435 p.
 [3]. Temam R. Uravneniya Nav’-e-Stoksa. Teoriya i chislennyi analiz // – M.: Mir, 1981. –386 p.
 [4].Fursikov A.V. Optimal’noe upravlenie raspredelennymi sistemami. Teoriya i

prilozheniya // – Novosibirsk: Nauchnaya kniga, 1999. – 352 p.

[5].Aisagaliev S.A., Belogurov A.P., Sevryugin I.V. K resheniyu integral'nogo uravneniya Fredgol'ma pervogo roda dlya funktsii neskol'kih peremennyh // Vestnik KazNU, ser.mat., meh., inf. – 2011. –№ 1 (68). – P. 21-30.

[6].Aisagaliev S.A., Belogurov A.P., Sevryugin I.V. Upravlenie teplovymi protsessami //Vestnik KazNU, ser. mat., meh., inf. – 2012, – № 1(72). – P. 14-26. (Rabota vypolnena pri podderzhke grantovogo finansirovaniya nauchno-tehnicheskikh programm Komiteta nauki MON RK, grant № 0696 / GF, 2012 - 2014 gg.)

[7].Aisagaliev S.A., Belogurov A.P. Upravlyaemost' i bystrodeistvie protsessa, opisyvaemogoparabolicheskim uravneniem s ogranichennym upravleniem // Sibirskii matematicheskiizhurnal. – 2012, – t. 53, № 1. – P. 20-37.